

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)
Milestone 16 – Topic Policy Day
Internal Note

Versions, first complete 29/2/2023

This milestone was holding a meeting with Scottish Government policy and analysis staff. The meeting was held via Teams with the presentations stored on the project website.

End of Year Presentations, 2022-23:

1. [Overview](#) - Keith Matthews
2. [Mitigation and Adaptation](#) - Mike Rivington
3. [Land Use Change Modelling](#) - Alessandro Gimona
4. [Peat Mapping](#) - Matt Aitkenhead
5. [Governance](#) - Kirsty Blackstock
6. [Story Telling](#) - Lee-Ann Sutherland
7. [Enhanced Conditionality](#) - Keith Matthews

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